

Management

USAGE OF VARIOUS GROUPS IN FACEBOOK-WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE AGE GROUP OF 18-30

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ABSTRACT

Facebook is very casual now-a-days for all persons in our society. Some of them have more than one account in facebook. Each person in facebook is in many pages and in more groups. But the matter is how they are get benefitted through these like additional features. Using this like groups has more beneficial to the users in many ways but it is in the hands of us to use facebook for good things or not. So the pros or cons whatever it may be, about this facebook and its features are in the way in which we use it. This paper fully deals with the usage of the various groups by the facebook users especially under the age group of 18-30.

Keywords:

Facebook, social networking service, Facebook groups.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Facebook is a social networking service as we know and it was launched in February 2004. It was founded by Mark Zuckerberg and his college roommates Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz and Chris Hughes and with fellow Harvard University. It was first created to communicate among the university students and later it became popularized worldwide and now-a-days it is being used by the most population in India and increasing in millions day by day.

The researchers stress mainly this age group because they are more interested than other age groups in becoming a members of groups like alumnus groups, entertainment groups, educational groups (recruitment/examinations groups).

Meaning of Groups:

Facebook Groups make it easy to connect with specific sets of people, like family, teammates or co-workers. Groups are private spaces where you can share updates, photos or documents and message other group members. You can also select one of three privacy options for each

group you create. It provides a closed space for small groups of people to communicate about shared interests. Groups can be created by anyone.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To the attitude and usage of groups in the face book account.

Profile of the Study Area:

The study area Sakthi Nagar is an area which is located 1 km away from Palayamkottai Market Area towards east. This area is located in between Samathanapuram and Shanthi Nagar areas. Different Community and religious people live together in this area. Population of this area is around 250 families. Most of the people in the study area belong to Hindu and Christian religion.

3. METHODOLOGY

Information was collected from 30 respondents from Sakthi Nagar during the period of January 10th-15th 2014. The researcher used a well framed questionnaire which consists of 17 questions. Primary data only used for this study. Respondents were selected on simple random sampling method. Collected data were analyzed with the statistical tools like tabulation, Percentile methods.

Important facts about Groups:

Privacy: In addition to an open setting, more privacy settings are available for groups. In secret and closed groups, posts are only visible to group members.

Audience: Group members must be approved or added by other members. When a group reaches a certain size, some features are limited. The most useful groups tend to be the ones you create with small groups of people you know.

Communication: In groups, members receive notifications by default when any member posts in the group. Group members can participate in chats, upload photos to shared albums, collaborate on group docs and invite members who are friends to group events.

How are Pages different from groups?

Pages allow real organizations, businesses, celebrities and brands to communicate broadly with people who like them. Pages may only be created and managed by official representatives.

Privacy: Page information and posts are public and generally available to everyone on Facebook.

Audience: Anyone can like a Page to connect with it and get News Feed updates. There is no limit to how many people can like a Page.

Communication: Page admins can share posts from their Page. Page posts can appear in the News Feeds of people who like the Page. Page admins can also create customized apps for their Page and check Page Insights to track the Page's growth and activity.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Table 1: Sex & age wise classification

Age	Male	Female	Total	percentage
18-21	18	6	14	40
22-25	12	6	18	30
26-30	12	6	18	30
Total	42	18	60	100
Percentage	70	30	100	

Source: Primary data

In our study, there are totally 30 respondents, among them 21 are male and 9 are female respondents. Respondents belonging to the age group of 18-21 years are lead in this table.

Facebook users in years:

Table 2: facebook users in years

Year	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Less than 1year	18	6	24	40
1-2years	6	12	18	30
2-3years	12	-	12	20
More than 3years	6	-	6	10
Total	42	18	60	100

Source: Primary data

The above table clearly shows that the respondents using facebook for less than 1 year are more (40%), and there is no female respondents using facebook for 2-3years and above 3years.

Respondents' satisfaction level about the groups:

Table 3: Satisfaction level about the groups

Level	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Highly satisfied	-	6	6	10
Satisfied	30	6	36	60
Neither	6	6	12	20
Dissatisfied	6	-	6	10
Highly Dissatisfied	-	-	-	-
Total	42	18	60	100

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is clearly infers that only 10% respondents are highly satisfied, 60% respondents are just satisfied and there is no respondent are highly dissatisfied.

5. FINDINGS

- There are totally 30 respondents in our study. Among them 21 are male and 9 are female respondents.
- Age group of 18-21 are more in our study (40%).
- Under Graduate students are of 50% in our research.
- Respondents using face book less than 1 year are more in number (40%).
- 80% of respondents have only one a/c in facebook.
- Respondents having memberships in 2 groups and more than 3 groups are 30% respectively.
- Also, respondents who are members in only one group and 3 groups are same 20%.
- Most respondents are members in entertaining groups and alumnis groups.
- Very few are members in religious and educational groups.
- 60% of respondents' visits their group regularly while rest of them no visit.
- No respondents are highly satisfied by the admins' involvement, while 60% just satisfied and 10% of each are dissatisfied and highly dissatisfied.
- Majority respondents (60%) told that the posts by the groups are somewhat good.
- Only 20% said that the posts are good and rest said that it is bad.
- 60% of respondents told that they are just satisfied about the groups they are members.
- Only 10% respondents told that they are highly satisfied about their groups, 20% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied and rests 10% are dissatisfied by their groups.

6. SUGGESTIONS

- Respondents are not satisfied in the involvement of admins in the group, it should be changed.
- Also they are not fully satisfied by the posts of the particular groups, for this, admins are fully responsible and satisfy their group members.
- Some respondents' lacks interest on the group they joined after some days; it's a duty of the group admins to recover this like un-interested persons to their group.
- Respondents feel that there are no more updates in the groups they belong to, so it should be taken consideration.
- Some respondents told that some posts are differ from the name of the groups. They are disturbed very much by this like posts also, so the admins are requested to post related matters to the group.
- Some respondents requested to post something in the group regularly because some groups are sitting simply after the first few posts.
- According to educational groups, some groups forget to post the answers for the questions they posted; it should be taken into consideration.
- The admins should communicate/interact with the members regularly to avoid these like problems.
- They should ask the feedbacks about the group's activities from the members and make changes if needed.

7. CONCLUSION

Creating a group is a simple work but adding more members in our group and maintaining them in touch is more difficult job. Many admins are failing in this step. Some of them are unable to post continuously although they have more creative ideas about their groups because of the changes in their life, also it is unavoidable.

They create a group in some eagerness at a fraction of second but after some days they don't know what to post and so they are posting some matters which are not relate to the group.

So the admins should pre-plan before create any group and then start the group, if there is any unavoidable circumstances to leave a group, they should make any of their close friends to manage the group, who has the ability to manage.

By following this like activities, admins can fulfil members' expectations regarding the posts and managing the groups.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] <https://www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook>
- [2] <https://www.facebook.com/help/155275634539412>